

A Prospective Study of Manifestations in Cases of Fungal Rhinosinusitis (FRS) and Their Management in A Tertiary Care Hospital: One Year Study

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Abstract:

Fungal rhinosinusitis (FRS) has increased over the past few decades which might be due to the rampant use of antibiotics, steroids, immunosuppressive drugs, increased incidence of HIV and uncontrolled state of diabetes. It is characterized by inflammation of the sinus mucosa due to fungal infection. *Aspergillus* species is the most common. Immunocompromised patients should take special precautions and should be aggressively treated should there be any suspicion of fungal sinusitis. The usual treatment for FRS involves surgery and aggressive medical management with close follow-up. The medical management includes anti-allergic medications, immunotherapy, and the addition of oral corticosteroids. Although medical management improves patient outcomes, more evidence regarding FRS management is still needed.

Keywords: Fungal, Rhinosinusitis, Nasal Blockage, Headache, Immunocompromised

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Introduction

Fungal rhinosinusitis (FRS), once considered a rare disease, has seen a steep rise in incidence in recent times. This rise in the burden of fungal disease is a consequence of an increment in the population with weakened immune systems like diabetes, excessive use of systemic corticosteroids, use of immunosuppressive drugs and chemo-radiotherapy. FRS represents a wide spectrum of diseases ranging from the mild form of superficial colonisation, and allergic manifestations to life-threatening extensive invasive disease.

Diagnosis of FRS has been a challenge as the presenting clinical signs and symptoms and radiographic manifestations are often nonspecific. Definitive diagnosis requires direct fungi identification and hence culture and microscopic examination remain the gold standard. Therapeutic dilemmas are another aspect of the management of FRS as despite the availability of new antifungal drugs, treatment is often empirical due to the non-availability of early diagnosis, rapid disease progression and high costs of antifungal drugs.

A description of the different types of FRS, their diagnosis and management has been presented.

Objectives:

1. To Identify the probable aetiology of fungal rhinosinusitis
2. To study the manifestation & management of fungal rhinosinusitis

Methodology:

Study Design: A prospective study.

Study Settings: Gauhati Medical College and Hospital, a tertiary care hospital.

Study Period: 1 year; April 1st, 2023 to March 31st 2024.

Data Collection: Cases were selected based on their clinical presentation; CT scan and MRI reports wherever applicable; IHC and fungal culture reports were also taken into consideration.

Case 1:

A 38-year-old male resident of ZOO ROAD in Kamrup Metro developed a progressive bilateral nasal blockage over 5 months. The patient did not experience headaches, foul-smelling nasal

discharge, dizziness, or emesis. No epistaxis was reported.

The individual mentioned nocturnal snoring, necessitating oral breathing. Examination revealed multiple pale, fleshy growths extending from both nostrils, indicative of bilateral ethmoidal polyps.

Computed tomography of the nose and paranasal sinuses showed complete opacification of both maxillary sinuses and nasal passages, extending to the choana. The imaging also demonstrated extensive soft tissue density occupying and obstructing the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses, with hyperdense components in the nasal cavity and both maxillary antra, as well as nasal cavity widening, suggesting fungal sinusitis. Other haematological parameters were within normal ranges. The patient initially received antifungal therapy and subsequently underwent Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) under general anaesthesia. During the procedure, yellowish spheres were discovered and submitted for histopathological examination and fungal culture analysis. Postoperatively, the patient was initiated on alkaline nasal douching to remove crusting. A biopsy of the mass confirmed it as a nasal polyp. Follow-up evaluations over the subsequent month revealed no evidence of recurrence.

Case 2:

A 41-year-old female was admitted to GMCH for facial asymmetry and ptosis of the eyeball on the right with facial swelling on the same side for the last 20 days. She also complained of Right-sided ear discharge which was profuse, purulent, foul-smelling, and yellowish and was associated with right-sided earache. She has also complained of diminished vision in the last 20 days in the right

eye. Her HbA1c was reported to be 11.8 (elevated). 24 urine proteins were also elevated. On Local examination, the rise of temperature over the right side of the face is present, tenderness over paranasal sinuses is present, On DNE thick blackish crusting over the right inferior turbinate and right middle turbinate, Polypoidal changes present over the right middle turbinate were noted, nasopharynx was congested. Otoendoscopy shows right ear subtotal perforation with non-tender polypoidal mass seen in EAC.

CEMRI of the Brain was showing features suggestive of fungal sinusitis with involvement of the right orbital apex causing resultant right ptosis, adjacent soft tissue inflammatory changes in the right retro-orbital and retro-antral fat space, masticator space and periorbital region. (D/D - mucormycosis). The histopathological investigation was done for tissue taken from growth in the hard palate, tissue from the right nostril mass, and tissue from the right ear canal, which shows infarcted tissue, dense neutrophilic infiltrate, and separate fungal hyphae with acutely angled branching on silver staining.

Fungal culture report suggestive of *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Antifungal medications (I.V Amphotericin B 1mg/kg/day for 2 weeks) were started with strict glycemic control and endoscopic debridement of sinonasal tissue was done. In the postoperative period, alkaline nasal douching was done, endoscopic nasal cleaning was done and antifungal therapy was continued as I.V. Voriconazole 4mg/kg twice daily for 1 month followed by oral voriconazole for 3 months was continued. The patient was under regular follow and till now no signs and symptoms of recurrence were noted.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Case 3: A 48-year-old female, presented with left nasal blockage and headache for the last 3 years. On examination, the patient was found to have bilateral sinonasal polyposis with left-sided deviated nasal septum. Initial CT Nose and PNS show soft tissue lesion with internal calcified foci noted in left ethmoidal air cells, mild bony erosion, and mild DNS noted towards the left. Following this she was started on nasal steroids spray for months, repeat ct nose and PNS shows mucosal thickening noted in left few posterior ethmoidal air cells, sphenothmoid recess, left sphenoid sinus,

extending to left superior meatus, left-sided DNS. She was treated with submucosal resection and functional endoscopic sinus surgery (left-sided middle meatal antrostomy with total ethmoidectomy with sphenoidotomy and right middle meatal antrostomy with anterior ethmoidectomy) under General Anaesthesia on 8/3/2024. Histopathological examination of tissue from the left ethmoid sinus showed mainly necrosis along with numerous fungal profiles, morphologically suggestive of *Aspergillus*. Sinus tissue or tumour tissue not seen. Upon discharge,

the patient was advised to oral voriconazole 200 mg once daily for 6 weeks and nasal douching with alkaline nasal wash. Follow-up was done to date

and no signs or symptoms of recurrence were noted.

Figure 3:

Case 4:

A 13-year-old male patient hailing from Udalguri has had right-sided nasal blockage and proptosis of the right side of the eye for the last 5 months which was gradually progressive. Later on, the patient suffered from right-sided loss of vision. History of one episode of epistaxis was there. It was there. It was associated with a right-sided headache. From the right nostril specimen; a punch biopsy was taken twice. Allergic fungal sinusitis was diagnosed and antifungal therapy was started.

Serum-specific IgE for fungus was positive. The mass appeared to have reduced. A decision for surgery was made. Right-sided subtotal maxillectomy with enucleation of the right eyeball with right external carotid artery ligation was done.

An excised mass was sent for HPE- which came out to be nasopharyngeal carcinoma. The tumour was extended to the infratemporal fossa, medially to the greater wing of the sphenoid, beyond the cavernous sinus. The patient followed up for the next 5 months and recurrence was reported.

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

Case 5:

A 35-year-old female was referred to GMCH with facial swelling, nose block, nasal discharge, and discharge from the medial canthus of both eyes, diminution of vision in Rt eye (hand movement), loose teeth, headache, ulcer in bilateral pre-zygomatic area.

Ct scan nose & pns s/o soft tissue in b/l maxillary sinus with the erosion of all walls of b/l maxillary sinus & b/l zygomatic possibly extending to upper alveolar process with the possibility of mucormycosis. MRI s/o of facial cellulitis with b/l orbits extending to the cavernous sinus, left middle cranial fossa, with inflammation changes of extraocular muscles, facial muscles, and intracoronar fat plane. Diagnostic nasal endoscopy is suggestive of inflammatory change of the

inferior turbinates on both sides with thick yellowish discharge in the middle meatus area on both sides from which nasal swab sent for fungal culture & fungal culture is suggestive of candida species which is sensitive to fluconazole, voriconazole, itraconazole, & resistant for Amphotericin B. After that, she has taken Itraconazole for 2 months & voriconazole for 1 months. Following this FESS was performed and all cells were opened under the coverage of systemic steroids & and tissue was sent for a histopathological examination it came out to be an Inflammatory polyp in the post-op period nasal douching was started for day 5. Upon discharge oral antifungals, and nasal douching, were advised. Pt went for plastic surgery for the facial deformity and followed up for the next 6 months.

Figure 7:

Figure 8:

Case 6:

A 38 year old male hailing from Baihata Chariali who was a shop keeper in profession (electronic

accessories) presented to opd with ulcerated area over left side of nostril and left nasolabial fold including alar cartilage. Upon equiring detailed history; patient was having bleeding from nose for

a few episodes on the year 2021, along with history of frequent cold, nasal obstruction with nasal pain. Later on he developed small nodular swelling on the floor of nostril, then a additional swelling of the outer surface of the left nostril.

The surrounding region around the left vestibule began to swell up which initiated pain sensation. Patient give history of rapid weight loss since last 3 months. Then he went for treatment at a private nursing care, where they took a biopsy from the lesion and it showed extensive necrosis and inflammatory debris with budding yeast forms and presence of hyphae which indicated towards fungal etiology. There he was tried with conservative therapy but it could not resolved the issue. After that patient presented to Gauhati Medical College and Hospital OPD, with painful swelling of nose

and face for last 4 months, there biopsy from the swelling was taken for histopathological examination and fungal culture. Fungal culture showed *Aspergillus Fumigatus*, histopathological features were suggestive of aspergilloma. MR study reveals mucosal thickening involving bilateral maxillary, bilateral ethmoidal, left frontal sinuses with atrophied left middle and inferior turbinates suggestive of chronic fungal rhinosinusitis. Tablet Posaconazole 300 mg once daily was started for a continuous period of 3 months along with multivitamin supplement. Later on Inj Liposomal Amphotericin B was started as 39 mg in 500 ml 5% dextrose IV slowly over 6 hours for a duration of 4 weeks. Regular monitoring of liver function test, renal function test, serum electrolytes was done during these course of treatment.

Figure 9:

Figure 10:

Patients may experience nasal block, nasal discharge, nasal bleeding, septal perforation, headaches, acute unilateral visual loss, and pain in the eye, facial disfigurement, thrombosis of the cavernous sinus or carotid-cavernous fistula. A fatal complication of invasive fungal rhinosinusitis is cavernous sinus or orbital apex aspergillosis. When both parts are affected, it is known as cavernous sinus-orbital apex syndrome.

Management

Surgical debridement is the treatment of choice for most cases of fungal sinusitis, as it is both diagnostic and therapeutic. Polypectomy should take place if indicated. Oral corticosteroids are beneficial in many acute and chronic fungal sinusitis (AFS) and improve symptoms by suppressing inflammation and lowering circulating IgE levels, although their prolonged use is discouraged.

Nasal topical steroids in combination with systemic steroids reduce the recurrence rate. Systemic

antifungals can be an adjunct treatment for invasive fungal rhinosinusitis. Amphotericin B may be the first drug of choice in the treatment of invasive fungal sinusitis because of its broad coverage of *Mucor* species and *Aspergillus*. The use of some azole antifungals could also be beneficial. It is manageable through nasal douching, which is the cleansing of the nasal sinuses with saline. Surgical management may comprise Endoscopic middle meatal antrostomy +total ethmoidectomysphenoidotomy- septoplasty.

Discussion

Allergic fungal rhinosinusitis (AFRS) is the most common non-invasive type of fungal rhinosinusitis. Patients with AFRS typically present with symptoms like nasal obstruction, discharge, and headaches. They often exhibit unilateral nasal polyps accompanied by thick yellowish-green discharge. In some cases, nasal polyps form an expansile mass that can cause bone necrosis in the thin sinus walls, potentially spreading to the orbital

area and resulting in proptosis (eye bulging) and vision loss. CT scans of these cases often reveal distinctive serpinginous sinus opacification, mucosal thickening, and bone erosion, though the “double density” sign seen on CT is not specific to AFRS and can also occur in fibrous dysplasia of the sinus.

Non-invasive FRS is typically considered when patients experience chronic rhinosinusitis symptoms that do not improve with standard treatments. Surgical intervention is essential for the effective management of FRS. In contrast, invasive fungal rhinosinusitis often occurs in immunocompromised patients and can rapidly advance, leading to extensive damage to the sinus walls, orbit, and hard palate, as well as skin and mucous membrane involvement. Severe symptoms like acute facial pain, vision loss, proptosis, cavernous sinus thrombosis, sepsis, and even septic shock may be present. Due to the slow turnaround time of fungal cultures (approximately three weeks), it is vital to begin antifungal treatment based on clinical history, physical examination, CT findings, and diagnostic nasal endoscopy (DNE) results rather than waiting for culture confirmation.

Discussion:

Fungal rhinosinusitis (FRS) is a multifaceted condition that presents significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges, particularly given its increasing incidence among immunocompromised patients. This rise may be attributed to a growing population with conditions that compromise immune defences, such as diabetes, and HIV, and the increased use of immunosuppressive therapies. FRS ranges widely in presentation, from non-invasive forms like allergic fungal rhinosinusitis (AFRS) to aggressive, invasive types, emphasizing the need for a thorough and individualized approach to management.

Timely and accurate diagnosis is crucial, as invasive forms can rapidly progress, leading to severe outcomes such as vision loss, facial deformities, or cavernous sinus thrombosis. Imaging modalities, particularly CT and MRI, are instrumental in defining disease extent, though they often lack specificity. Thus, fungal culture and histopathological examination remain the gold standard, despite inherent delays in obtaining results. Given this delay, empirical antifungal therapy is sometimes initiated based on clinical suspicion, particularly in rapidly progressing cases. Management strategies often include a combination of surgical debridement and antifungal medication. Surgical intervention is essential not only for disease control but also for obtaining diagnostic tissue samples. Medications such as Amphotericin B and azole antifungals are typically employed, though challenges remain due to the high cost,

potential side effects, and sometimes limited efficacy in certain cases.

This study underscores that while individualized care and vigilant follow-up have been effective in reducing recurrence rates, further research is necessary to refine treatment protocols and explore more cost-effective options. Additionally, the complexity of FRS cases, particularly in tertiary care settings, highlights the importance of multidisciplinary collaboration to improve patient outcomes.

Conclusion

Fungal rhinosinusitis (FRS) is increasingly prevalent, especially in immunocompromised individuals, presenting as a spectrum from mild to severe invasive disease. Prompt diagnosis and intervention are critical, with imaging like CT and MRI aiding in assessment, while fungal culture confirms diagnosis. This study highlights diverse FRS cases, showing that management often requires a combination of surgical debridement, antifungal therapy, and supportive care. Early treatment is essential in invasive forms to prevent severe complications.

Despite advancements, challenges remain due to treatment costs and rapid disease progression, underscoring the need for individualized care and further research to improve outcomes.

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